

TWENTY-SECOND International Conference on composite materials (iccm22)

Validation and Application of Micro-CT Analysis for Recycled Carbon Fiber Card Web Reinforced Thermoplastics

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❑ Introduction

- ▶ Research background
- ▶ Carding process to re-manufacture rCF
- ▶ Prediction of the mechanical properties by using FOD

❑ Validation of Micro-CT analysis method

- ▶ Micro-CT analysis
- ▶ Objective material
- ▶ Mechanical properties
- ▶ Image processing and data analysis

❑ Application of Micro-CT analysis method

❑ Conclusion

CFRP (Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastics)

CFRP^[1]

Applications^[2]

- ▶ Aerospace
- ▶ Automotive
- ▶ Wind energy
- ▶ Sporting goods

Market Forecast^[3]

an estimated increase of 60-times by 2030

r-CFRP

- ▶ Re-manufacture
- ▶ Re-use

r-CF (recycled carbon fiber)^[4]

CFRP recycling

- ▶ Mechanical recycling
- ▶ pyrolysis process
- ▶ fluidized bed processes
- ▶ chemical recycling

[1] "The Japan Carbon Fiber Manufacturers Association". <http://www.carbonfiber.gr.jp/>
 [2] Pickering J. "Composite materials in the Airbus A380 -From History to Future", ICCM13, Beijing, China, 2011.
 [3] Holmes, M. "Global carbon fibre market remains on upward trend". Reinforced Plastics, Vol. 58, No. 6, pp 38-45. 2014.
 [4] "IRECE Project". <http://www.susracproject.com/ireceproject/situation.html>

Carding Process to re-manufacture rCF

- Carding process[5] of CWT (Carbon fiber card Web reinforced Thermoplastics)

*Conducted by Ehime Institute of Paper Technology Center

[5] H30炭素繊維不織布パネル

Mechanical properties

Parameters

Type	Tensile test	3-point bending test
Reference standard	ISO 527-4	JIS K 7017
Testing machine	AUTOGRAPH AG-Xplus 250kN	AUTOGRAPH AGS-X 5kN
Load speed	1 mm/min	1 mm/min
Specimen number	5	5
Materials	filmCWT-10; filmCWT-20; CWT-20; CWT-30	filmCWT-10; filmCWT-20; CWT-20; CWT-30
Size	Length: 110 mm	Length: 50 mm
	Width: 15 mm	Width: 10mm
	Thickness: 3.0 mm	Thickness: 2.0 mm
	Holder length: 15 mm	Span/thickness: 16:1

Tensile test

3-point bending test

* CWT-10 refers to CWT with fiber volume fraction (V_f) 10%

* Film means PA6 film is added to change the V_f : CWT-30 + PA6 \Rightarrow filmCWT-20 & filmCWT-20

□ Results and conclusions

Tensile property of CWT: (a) tensile modulus, (b) tensile strength

□ Results and conclusions

Flexural property of CWT: (a) Flexural modulus, (b) Flexural strength

Applications of CWT

❑ The road towards mass applications

Crash safety

Joint parts
(B-pillar)

Shock-absorber

S-shape

T-shape

- ▶ CWT can be applied on some parts of the cars, which do not require high performance in both directions.

- ▶ Wrinkles in S-shape structures bending part might cause the degradation of mechanical properties.
- ▶ *Why the wrinkles occurred and how to avoid them?*

Theories to predict mechanical properties

Netting Theory

Correlation between fiber direction and coordinate system

Correlation between FOD and strength moduli

Laminate Theory

Discontinuous CFRP laminate can be equivalent to the combination of Unidirectional CFRP laminate [8]

Unidirectional CFRP lamina with arbitrary direction

$$\int_0^\pi f(\theta) d\theta = 1.0$$

$$E_{11} = E_f V_f \int_0^\pi \cos^4 \theta f(\theta) d\theta \quad \Rightarrow \quad E_L = E_{11} - \left(\frac{E_{12}^2}{E_{22}} \right)$$

$$E_{22} = E_f V_f \int_0^\pi \sin^4 \theta f(\theta) d\theta \quad \Rightarrow \quad E_T = E_{22} - \left(\frac{E_{12}^2}{E_{11}} \right)$$

$$E_{12} = E_f V_f \int_0^\pi \sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \theta f(\theta) d\theta \quad \Rightarrow \quad E_{LT} = E_{12}$$

$$E_{xx} = \left(\frac{\cos^4 \theta}{E_1} + \frac{\sin^4 \theta}{E_2} + \frac{\sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \theta}{G_{12}} - 2\nu_{12} \frac{\sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \theta}{E_1} \right)^{-1}$$

$$E_{yy} = \left(\frac{\cos^4 \theta}{E_2} + \frac{\sin^4 \theta}{E_1} + \frac{\sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \theta}{G_{12}} - 2\nu_{12} \frac{\sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \theta}{E_1} \right)^{-1}$$

$$E_L = \int_0^\pi E_{xx} f(\theta) d\theta \quad \Rightarrow \quad E_T = \int_0^\pi E_{yy} f(\theta) d\theta$$

Since Vf can be obtained by ash test, the only unknown here is $f(\theta)$, the **fiber orientation distribution(FOD)**.

[8]前川善一路, 山田真司, 加地秋好, 溝内博行. "繊維配向分布を考慮した繊維強化複合材料の剛性と変形の推定", 材料, Vol. 39, No. 441, (1990), pp. 667-673.

Measurement of FOD : Micro-CT analysis

Measurement of FOD by X-ray Micro-CT analysis method

Schematic of scanning process^[7]

Description of fiber orientation in 3-dimension

In-plane fiber binarization

Micrographs of cross-ply plate

[7] Y. Wan, I. Straumit, J. Takahashi, S. Lomov, "Micro-CT analysis of internal geometry of chopped carbon fiber tapes reinforced thermoplastics". Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing. Vol. 91, pp 211-221. 2016.

□ Research Objectives

- ▶ **Confirm the validity of the x-ray CT analysis method**
 - ▶ Since this is the first time we put X-ray Micro-CT analysis method into use, one specific material should be used to confirm the validity of the x-ray CT analysis method.
- ▶ **Confirm the proper settings of the analysis software**
 - ▶ So that it can not only be applied to CWT, but also other novel materials.
- ▶ **Predict the mechanical properties of CWT**
- ▶ **Predict the mechanical properties of complex structures made by CWT**
 - ▶ Use x-ray CT analysis method to obtain the predicted mechanic properties in both bending part and smooth part, which can hardly obtained by manual test. Figure out Why the wrinkles occurred and how to avoid them.

❑ UD CFRTP (Uni-directional Carbon Fiber Reinforced Thermoplastics)

➤ Based on fiber length distribution (FLD), the CFRTP composite forms:

FLD	Low	Middle	High	Highest
Type of composite system	Injection molded 			
Volume fraction (V_f)	Relatively low	Middle (20-30%)	High ($\geq 50\%$)	High ($\geq 50\%$)
Formability	Superior	General	Superior	Directional dependent
FOD	Process dependent	Process dependent	Designable	Designable

➤ UD CFRTP can be used to confirm the validity of the x-ray CT analysis method and the proper setting of the analysis software.

Research procedures

Carbon Fiber	TR50S-15K-GF	TR50S PP用
Resin	PA6	PP
Vf	54	45
Thickness	132 μm	100μm
		E1=240GPa

- ▶ The accuracy of the X-ray CT method can be determined by comparing the theoretical values with the experimental ones.

Validation of Micro-CT analysis method

Results of Tensile test

Tensile property of UD CFRTP Laminate: (a) tensile modulus, (b) tensile strength

Fracture diagram of Unidirectional UD laminates

Fracture diagram of Crossply UD laminates

Validation of Micro-CT analysis method

Results of FOD

FOD of Cross-ply laminates

FOD of Unidirectional laminates

Specimen	[0~45]+[135~180] [%]	[45~135] [%]
Cross-ply	48.86	51.14

Specimen	[0~45]+[135~180] [%]	[45~135] [%]
Unidirectional	99.98	0.02

Validation of Micro-CT analysis method

□ The comparisons of the prediction data and experiment results

Specimen	Experiment [Gpa]	Netting theory [Gpa]	Laminate Theory [Gpa]
UD Crossply	51.34	62.33	65.16
UD Unidirectional	91.73	106.88	108.61

Application of Micro-CT analysis method

Results of FOD of CWT-30

L-direction

T-direction

Specimen	[0~45]+[135~180] [%]	[45~135] [%]
CWT-30-L	76.74	23.26

Specimen	[0~45]+[135~180] [%]	[45~135] [%]
CWT-30-L	58.70	41.30

Application of Micro-CT analysis method

□ The comparisons of the prediction data and experiment results

Specimen	Experiment [Gpa]	Netting theory [Gpa]	Laminate Theory [Gpa]
CWT-30-L	30.83	42.08	43.45
CWT-30-T	16.36	31.48	33.40

❑ Conclusions

- ▶ A novel rCFRP material called carbon fiber card web reinforced thermoplastics (**CWT**) was proposed to close the CF recycling loop.
- ▶ Tensile test and three-point bending test were performed to obtain the corresponding **mechanical properties**.
- ▶ **The accuracy of the X-ray CT analysis method** have been verified by comparing the theoretical values of UD with the experimental ones. As predicted, the X-ray CT method can realize high accuracy measurement.
- ▶ **The FOD of CWT** were obtained by using the X-ray CT method and the theoretical values of mechanical properties were calculated and compared with experimental ones.